

Preliminary Investigation of The GC Content of the MC1R Gene in Birds and the Effect on its Plumage

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ABSTRACT

The study explores correlations between GC content and plumage in various avian species for understanding evolutionary or environmental adaptations. Using the GC content values of the MC1R gene in avians, this study covers the effect of this gene on its plumage. Therefore, R was used to statistically explain and visualize the genetic data provided by the NCBI database. After analyzing the necessary data, several discoveries were unveiled. First, the GC content was calculated using the absolute minimum possible value by counting all undetermined nucleotides N as neither a guanine nor a cytosine. This created some correlations. When the GC content of the MC1R gene is low in an avian, their plumage is likely to change, but not necessarily light. On the other hand, when the GC content is high, the avians will likely have darker feathers; therefore, their feathers will be less likely to change colors as easily due to the dark melanin. Then, after some revising and adding a five percent winsorization for outliers and applying it, it seems that the hue can correlate fairly well with the MC1R gene compared to other indicators related to the color of the birds' dominant feather plumage. In addition, since the low GC content of the birds' MC1R gene also relates to the cyan color well, it may be effective for reflectivity like in fish.

Keywords: birds, genomic analysis, MC1R gene, bird plumage, R code, biostatistics

1. INTRODUCTION

The MC1R gene is widely used when scientists analyze bird plumage because it tends to correlate with the polymerization of melanin in birds (Ng and Li, 2018). Using the popular topic, this study will expound and further support the claim that MC1R heavily affects plumage (Nam et al., 2010). More specifically, this will broaden the two species described in "Conserved genetic basis of a quantitative plumage trait involved in mate choice", which states that in both the lesser snow geese and arctic skuas, the variation of the MC1R gene is associated with melanism (Mundy et al., 2004). To support the claim, this study will focus on the variations of MC1R's GC content to a wider sample of bird species (n = 40).

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Aim of the Study

The purpose of this study is to understand the dynamics between the GC Content of the MC1R gene to see how it affects the coloration of different bird plumage. It can potentially help with research to find correlations between genomics and the coloration of more species.

2.2 Research Design

This is an explanatory sequential research to understand the effects of the GC Content of the MC1R gene on bird plumage. The dependent variable is the types of birds, and the independent variables include the approximate hex code for bird plumage and GC content of the MC1R gene as well as their results in terms of r-squared correlations and two-tailed p-tests.

2.3 Hypothesis

The null hypothesis is that MC1R's GC content has no effect on bird plumages, whereas the alternative hypothesis is that MC1R's GC content does have an effect on bird plumages.

2.4 Databases and Samples Used

Species (Common Name)	Accession Number
Chicken	NC_052542.1
Turkey	NC_015023.2
Ruddy Duck	NC_048903.1
Okarito Brown Kiwi	NW_020450929.1
Chilean tinamou	NW_020455460.1
Rock Pigeon	NC_088614.1
Mallard	NC_051783.1
Swift Parrot	NC_088909.1
White-Crowned Sparrow	NC_088181.1

White-Crowned Manakin	NC_087562.1
House Sparrow	NC_087485.1
Tawny-Flanked Prinia	NC_086259.1
Song Sparrow	NC_086206.1
Night Parrot	NW_026913457.1
Bourke's Parrot	NW_026902017.1
Barn Swallow	NC_053460.1
Ground Parrot	NW_026636878.1
Lanner Falcon	NC_079302.1
Peregrine Falcon	NC_073734.1
Saker Falcon	NC_073710.1
California Condor	NC_059482.1
Mariana Crow	NW_024581064.1
Swainson's Thrush	NC_046231.1
Kakapo	NC_044302.2
Emperor Penguin	NW_008794602.1
Blue-Crowned Manakin	NW_016690234.1
Great Tit	NC_031780.1
Ruff	NW_015090842.1
Common Starling	NW_014650522.1
Tibetan Ground-Tit	NW_005087658.1

North Island Brown Kiwi	NW_013994796.1
Swan Goose (Sichuan White Goose)	NW_025927738.1
Bald Eagle	NW_010973104.1
Kea	NW_009920693.1
Chimney Swift	NW_009952441.1
Rifleman	NW_008673812.1
Carmine Bee-Eater	NW_008630915.1
Anna’s Hummingbird	NC_044257.1
Medium Ground-Finch	NW_005054373.1
Zebra Finch	NC_044223.2

Table 1: *MC1R Gene References for 40 Bird Species*

Note: All birds used and taken from the NCBI database (n = 40).

All nucleotide sequences and data are directly taken from the NCBI database (see Table 1 for more details). All the color data was added using the closest color approximation for each bird’s plumage. Those colors were then converted into hex codes. Only genes with an MC1R Gene ID, excluding aliases, with only sequence ascension numbers beginning with NC or NW and containing FASTA sequences, were used to obtain the best samples. When research began, the number of samples available after searching “mc1r aves” in the database consisted of 40 usable sequences. Therefore, those 40 species were used.

2.5 Assessments and Measures

GC content was calculated using R and the databases the author has compiled and was further analyzed. This research used the r-squared value. However, an additional two-tailed p-test was conducted afterward independently of the code where it was tested for $p < 0.1$ due to sample size constraints.

2.6 Summary of the Programs Created by the Author

Two programs were created to calculate the GC content. The first was calculated by calculating GC content by looking at the absolute minimum possible GC compared to bird

plumage. This was done by counting undetermined nucleotides labeled N alongside the same category as adenine and thymine. While the original intent differed, it did produce interesting results. The second was winsorized by 5% and excluded all unreadable nucleotides marked with N. Winsoriation is used to avoid extreme outliers that may significantly affect the results.

2.7 Adjusted Measurements

The zebra finch color was adjusted for the second program after noticing that the data said it was red (#FF4500). It was adjusted to the appropriate dominant plumage color, which is gray.

3. RESULTS

The results revealed four interesting findings: two were found using the first program, and the other two were discovered through the second program. Figures 1 and 2 show that white plumage can have a diverse value range.

3.1 If the MC1R GC Content includes undefined values to the total gene pool (GC / ATGCN)

As mentioned earlier, the initial code was not the main intention of the study, but the results did reveal interesting results.

3.1.1 High GC Content Indicates Darker Bird Plumage

Figure 1: Correlation of MC1R GC Content with Feather Color (Minimum Possible)

Note. This was created by Shuhei Miyairi using the NCBI database and R.

Figure 1 shows that most birds with a GC content of over 0.7 have darker and more subdued plumage. For example, emperor penguins (#000000, 0.8571) and peregrine falcons (#2F4F4F, 0.7272) have relatively dark plumage compared to other species in the dataset. The main exception is the Bourke Parrot, which has pink feathers.

3.1.2 Low GC Content Indicates the Potential of Diversity of Phenotypes

Likewise, low GC content indicates varying feather plumage possibilities for the species. For example, Figure 1 shows that the birds under 0.45, which are rock pigeons (0.3333) and zebra finches (0.4000), tend to have diverse plumage. Zebra finches tend to have red or yellow pigments based on their genes and diet of seeds (Cook, 2016). Rock pigeons’ color pattern can also vary, despite being usually a blue-ish color (Cornell Lab of Ornithology, 2019).

3.2 If the MC1R GC Content excludes undefined values to the total gene pool (GC / ATGC)

This was the original intent of the research. After reprogramming and readjusting, the results reveal two new findings.

3.2.1 If the MC1R GC Content Is Less than 0.61, the Plumage Is Likely A Vivid Sky Blue, Green, Pink, or Red.

Figure 2: Correlation of MC1R GC Content with Feather Color (Excluding Undeterminable Genomes Labeled N)

Note. This was created by Shuheii Miyairi using the NCBI database. All values have been 5% winsorized. The data has been outputted by R ($\sigma = 0.02409388$, $Mdn = 0.6182164$, $\mu = 0.6216179$, $min = 0.5751285$, $max = 0.6533894$, $n = 40$).

Figure 3: *GC Content Across Bird Species with Hex Colors*

Note. This is the same data as Figure 2, but adjusted by species and in order from lowest GC content to highest GC content.

Figure 3 orders the colors by least to most GC content. As visually seen, values below 0.61 tend to have more vivid colors than those above 0.61.

3.2.2 Hue of Bird Plumage Correlates the Most with the MC1R Gene

Criteria for Color	R ² Correlation for Criteria and GC Content of the MC1R Gene of Avians
H	0.1256564
S	0.0489790
V	0.0154255
R	0.0257730
G	0.0081582

B	0.0171830
C	0.0766165
M	0.0028642
Y	0.0391572
K	0.0154255

Table 2: *R-squared Value for the Correlation Between the Criteria for Color and the GC Content of the MC1R Gene of Avians*

Note. This was created by Shuhei Miyairi. All values have been calculated using R. All genomic data was taken from NCBI. H represents hue, S represents saturation, V represents value, R represents red, G represents green, B represents blue, C represents cyan, M represents magenta, Y represents yellow, and K represents black. The values for V and K are the same because the value is another word for blackness. These R values are based on Figures 4 to 13.

Figure 4: *The Correlation between Hue and GC Content of the MC1R Genes of Avians*

Note. This was created by Shuhei Miyairi using the NCBI database and R based on the values shown in Figure 2.

Figure 5: *The Correlation between Saturation and GC Content of the MC1R Genes of Avians*

Note. This was created by Shuheii Miyairi using the NCBI database and R based on the values shown in Figure 2.

Figure 6: *The Correlation between Value and GC Content of the MC1R Genes of Avians*

Note. This was created by Shuheii Miyairi using the NCBI database and R based on the values shown in Figure 2.

Figure 7: *The Correlation between Redness and GC Content of the MC1R Genes of Avians*
Note. This was created by Shuheii Miyairi using the NCBI database and R based on the values shown in Figure 2.

Figure 8: *The Correlation between Greenness and GC Content of the MC1R Genes of Avians*
Note. This was created by Shuheii Miyairi using the NCBI database and R based on the values shown in Figure 2.

Figure 9: *The Correlation between Blueness and GC Content of the MC1R Genes of Avians*
Note. This was created by Shuhei Miyairi using the NCBI database and R based on the values shown in Figure 2.

Figure 10: *The Correlation between Cyanness and GC Content of the MC1R Genes of Avians*
Note. This was created by Shuhei Miyairi using the NCBI database and R based on the values shown in Figure 2.

Figure 11: *The Correlation between Magentaness and GC Content of the MC1R Genes of Avians*

Note. This was created by Shuheii Miyairi using the NCBI database and R based on the values shown in Figure 2.

Figure 12: *The Correlation between Yellowness and GC Content of the MC1R Genes of Avians*

Note. This was created by Shuheii Miyairi using the NCBI database and R based on the values shown in Figure 2.

Figure 13: *The Correlation between Yellowness and GC Content of the MC1R Genes of Avians*

Note. This was created by Shuheii Miyairi using the NCBI database and R based on the values shown in Figure 2.

Table 2 combines all the data from Figures 4 to 13. All the criteria except for magenta and green are considered significant. This is because all r-squared values above 0.01 are considered statistically significant in genetics (Hoggart et al., 2023). Out of these, it correlates most closely with hue, followed by cyan. Figure 10 shows that cyan is negatively correlated with the GC content of the birds' MC1R gene.

Criteria for Color	Two-tailed p-test value for Criteria and GC Content of the MC1R Gene of Avians
H	0.024815
S	0.169938
V	0.445129
R	0.322378
G	0.579393

B	0.420101
C	0.083797
M	0.742926
Y	0.220961
K	0.445129

Table 3: Two-tailed p-value for the Correlation Between the Criteria for Color and the GC Content of the MC1R gene

Note. This table is based on the values of Table 2, and the number of samples (n = 40).

Additionally, Table 3 shows that when conducting the two-tailed p-value test based on Table 2, both hue and the cyan factors had a p-value of under 0.1, which further strengthens the point that the MC1R gene both hue and cyan are statistically significant.

4. DISCUSSION

White plumage is likely to have a wide range of GC content because no bird plumage is truly white, and has a slight color in them. The biggest potential reason that the first code yielded low GC content for birds with variable plumage is that those genomes can easily mutate to produce a variety. This makes it more difficult to detect the exact nucleotides. When the GC content excludes unidentifiable nucleotides labeled N, higher concentrations of adenine and thymine tend to correlate with more cyan and vivid colors. These are consistent with the melanin reflections described in a study conducted by Okazaki. The visible reflection intensity of blue and green birds, such as the blue and green parrots, have high melanin and low concentration of light, whereas the visible reflection intensity of red and yellow birds, such as the red and yellow parrots, have low melanin and high concentration of light (Okazaki, 2020). It is reasonable to hypothesize that lower GC contents in the MC1R gene of avians reflect their sky-blue environment better. This phenomenon is just like how fish tend to have lower GC contents relative to other vertebrate species (Matoulek et al., 2023) helping bolster the effectiveness of their reflectable guanine platelets from their bodies that act to be effective photonic crystals (Iwasaka, 2020).

5. CONCLUSION

The GC content of the MC1R gene is a good indicator to help clarify which aspects of bird plumage color it influences the most. The major result was that relative to other values tested, the overall hue was the most influenced by the MC1R; this was even true even more than certain colors. However, if a certain color had to be chosen, it would be the color of cyan, which is reflective of the colors of Earth's nature. Therefore, considering that the results showed that there were statistically significant values, especially for the correlation between the hue of bird plumage with the GC content of the MC1R gene, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

6. LIMITATIONS

The primary setback in this experiment is the lack of reliable genetic data. However, in the future, with the number of reliable genetic data increasing, it is worth reinvestigating in the future.

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